

TRANSPARENCY- ORIENTED PROCESS CHECKLIST (TPC)

N _o	ITEMS	YES	NO	N/A	OBSERVATIONS
LANES					
POOL					
1	Are the pools clearly described in the BPMN model, i.e., do they represent an organizational participant or the process name when referencing a main process?				
2	Does the Pool in the process model use terminology specific to the application domain?				
3	Is the Pool easily and directly identified in the process model descriptions?				
4	Does the Pool labeling follow the standard of capitalizing the first letter of each word (Title Case)?				
5	Do the pools in the model adequately reflect the process context, representing the participants and their respective activities in the lanes?				
FLOW OBJECTS					
ACTIVITIES					
6	Are all activities that are immediately after the start event and before the end event positioned in the correct lanes?				
7	Does the activity name in the model correspond to the action to be performed and its functions in the process?				
8	Does the activity name in the model correspond to the action to be performed and its functions in the process?				
9	Does each process activity have its label started with an infinitive verb, followed by a noun, and contain 1 to 5 words, without conjunctions?				
10	Are the descriptions of the activities in the process model concise, focusing on essential aspects, with operational details recorded in annotations, for example?				
11	Is there information in the "Activities" that indicates they should be represented by other elements (type: events, data objects, annotations)?				
12	Are there overly complex activities that, to align with the desired level of abstraction, require subdivision into multiple smaller activities or a new process?				
13	Is there an activity that would be more effectively represented as a subprocess to improve modularity and reusability within the model?				

LEGENDA

N/A (Não se aplica)

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14	Does the sequence of activities demonstrate coherence and alignment with the established process model, ensuring a flow that meets organizational needs?				
15	Are there activities that do not contribute to the defined objectives of the process model and affect the correct representation of concurrent activities?				
16	Have activities considered essential to the process model been omitted?				
17	Are critical activities to the process model inadequately described?				
18	Are there similar or identical activities in different pools/lanes?				
EVENTS					
19	Is the start event represented in the model and named with the term "Start" (or "Início"), to indicate the initial point of the process?				
20	Is the end event represented in the model and named with the term "End" (or "Fim"), to indicate the terminal point of the process?				
21	Do intermediate events, except for timer and connector events, have descriptions starting with a noun, indicating what is being sent, followed by a past participle verb (e.g., "model inspected")?				
22	Are intermediate events adequately assigned to the lanes of those responsible for generating them?				
23	Are intermediate events adequately assigned to the lanes of those responsible for generating them?				
24	Do connection intermediate events, such as "Link" events, labeled with a noun, show the sending and receiving to connect process sections, avoiding sequence flow crossings?				
25	For each intermediate event, are the respective responsibilities (role and its contribution) well-defined in the process flow, in the sense that they must occur for the process to be executed?				
26	Are events based on temporal conditions aligned with the specific needs of the process, indicating a temporal condition to be met?				
27	Is the labeling of timer events presented with a gerund verb and a temporal indicator, to facilitate immediate identification of its role in the process?				
28	Do gateways ensure proper synchronization between activity flows?				

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GATEWAYS					
29	Are the conditions established in the outgoing flows of Gateways precise, clearly defined, and viable for the process model?				
30	Are the labels of gateway outputs unambiguously described?				
31	Do the combinations of events and gateways correctly reflect all execution scenarios of the process model?				
32	Do the combinations of events and gateways correctly reflect all execution scenarios of the process model?				
33	Do annotations in the process model exclusively contain additional and relevant information about the process?				
ARTIFACTS					
ANNOTATIONS					
34	Is it possible to convert some annotations into "Events" or "Activities" to improve the clarity, efficiency, and functionality of the model?				
35	Do the labels of data objects offer interpretability, representing an applicable state and facilitating immediate identification of their functions and uses within the process?				
DATA OBJECTS					
36	Do the data objects represent a repository of information (database, systems) to be persisted?				
37	Are the data objects consulted by the activities associated with them?				
38	Are data objects linked to the process model labeled using a noun?				
39	Does the arrangement of data objects represent the data manipulation behaviors generated or consumed by the activity?				

PROCESS CHECKLIST

Versão 1.1

No	ITEMS	YES	NO	N/A	OBSERVATIONS
OBJETOS DE CONEXÃO					
FLAWS					
40	Are the data association arrows from data objects to activities correct?				
MODEL DIAGRAM					
41	Does the header present the information: author identification, version, and description of the process model?				
42	Does the description in the model header explicitly state the objective of the process model concisely?				
43	Does the process model minimize the number of sequence flow crossings between elements?				
44	Do all elements used in the model follow a font size standard?				
45	Do all elements used in the model follow a font size standard?				
46	Do all elements used in the model follow an element size standard?				
47	Does the labeling of model elements follow a consistent style, with activity labels centered, for example?				
48	Are there elements or information in the model that could be removed, keeping only essential data for its interpretation?				
49	Are there inconsistencies or contradictions between elements in the BPMN model (e.g., subsequences of activities or gateways that are mutually exclusive)?				
50	Are there inconsistencies or contradictions that affect the integrity and executability of the model?				
51	Is the process model accessible, for example, is the access link or sharing location made available?				

Horário final: